

**Dendrochronological analysis of altarpiece, Kvæfjord 2, Norway
C3216**

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In this report, the non-invasive dendrochronological analysis of the altarpiece called Kvæfjord 2, Norway, is described.

This research was commissioned to contribute to the PhD research of Kristin Kausland, within the research project, 'After the Black Death: Painting and Polychrome Sculpture in Norway, 1350–1550'. This project is co-led by Noëlle Streeton and Tine Frøysaker, based in Conservation Studies, University of Oslo (UiO). Funding for this study was issued to Noëlle Streeton and Kristin Kausland in 2013 by the Department of Archaeology, Conservation and History (IAKH) and the Faculty of Humanities, UiO.

Fig. 1. Kvæfjord 2 altarpiece. View of the corpus.

Fig. 2. Kvæfjord 2 altarpiece. Schematic diagram of the wood elements in the altarpiece. The elements analysed are marked in green.

The altarpiece consists of a corpus and two wings. Tree-rings were not visible on any of the sculptures, but planking of both the corpus and both wings could be analysed non-invasively (marked in green, fig. 2). The corpus consists of an oak box, with three equally dimensioned backing planks and four narrower planks forming the sides, and with a narrow stage (fig. 1 and fig. 2). The corpus had three figures (not examined) and is adorned with a single tracery element carved from a single oak piece (fig. 1). The wings also both consist of a backing plank, narrower sides and a plank stage.

Measuring

As described in the report on the dendrochronological analysis of the Slagen altarpiece (*CATS dendro report 2*, Daly 2013b), non-invasive analysis can be carried out in certain circumstances, and this was a priority for the altarpieces being analysed in this project. Tree-ring measurements from the Kvæfjord 2 altarpiece were taken from parts where the wood grain was already exposed, and no invasive methods were used. The longitudinal section of the wood was exposed on the planks analysed (e.g. see fig. 8). Macro photographs were taken on the first visit to examine this object, on 17th September 2013, but as many of these photos were not of sufficient clarity for reliable measurement, the object was re-visited in July 2014, to make a second attempt. The second batch of photographs, where meticulous care was taken to adjust

the lighting angle for the photography, were very clear. It was from these new photographs, along with a ruler for scale and stitched together using Adobe Photoshop (version 11.0.2), that the tree-ring measurements were taken (using an application "Able Image Analyser"). Here, the scale is used to calibrate the picture, and the measurements are made to 1/100mm precision. For calculation of the t-value ("t-test") "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) is used, embedded in the program "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997).

Fig. 3. Kvæfjord 2 altarpiece. Mark on plank 3 (corpus, back plank 3).

The results

There are three backing planks forming the Corpus, each of very similar dimensions, and these are mounted vertically. The left and right hand side backing planks have a very similar appearance in that they both are made from very slow grown oak trees, while the middle backing plank is of a faster grown oak. Back plank 3 (see fig. 2 for plank numbers) has an incised housemark (Rief 2006) preserved (shown in fig. 3). Back plank 1 seems also to have a partially preserved housemark (figs. 8 & 9). No sapwood is observed on any of the backing planks. The tree-ring curves from the two backing planks with housemarks preserved are very similar. So similar that it is possible that the planks were fashioned from the same tree. These two do not achieve highly significant correlation with the remaining timber from this altarpiece (table 1), suggesting that they are from a different region than the rest, and these two are averaged to one mean curve (Z102S001&3) to represent the tree that was used to make them. This average is 286 years long and covers the period AD 1199-1484.

Allowing for missing sapwood, the tree used to make these two planks was felled after AD 1494 (see fig. 5).

The correlation between the remaining tree-ring curves, including the middle backing planks, all four side planks and the tracery making up the corpus, and planks from both the left and right wings, are also shown in table 1, and these are averaged to a mean curve (Z102M006), 229 years long covering the period AD 1262-1490.

Two side planks forming the left wing of the altarpiece, planks 12 & 14, display such high agreement both statistically ($t = 9.71$) and visually, that these two are probably made from the same tree. These are however not dated.

Fig. 4. Kvæfjord 2 altarpiece. Mark on plank 7 (corpus, bottom plank of box).

Interpretation

The chronological positions of the dated timbers is shown in fig. 5. None of the timbers have sapwood preserved. The outermost preserved tree-ring in the group (on plank 2, the middle backing plank of the corpus (Z102002c)) was formed in AD 1490. The estimated felling date for the tree that this plank comes from is estimated to be after AD 1500 (marked in orange). Construction details on the corpus box suggest that the three backing planks were added to the caisse using a different carpentry, and therefore there is the suggestion that the back planks were added later in the caisse construction process. The dendrochronology cannot finally confirm this, but the fact that two of the back planks (P1 & P3) do not belong with the main group of timbers

does allow the suggestion that the back is from a different timber source, and we might speculate that this also suggests a different chronology. As no sapwood is preserved however, this evidence is only circumstantial. If the dating of the backing planks is later (marked in orange in fig. 5) then we might suggest that the main construction is from slightly earlier – i.e. after AD 1492 (marked in green fig. 5). Again, this is speculative, as no sapwood is preserved.

Fig. 5. Kvæfjord 2 altarpiece. Diagram showing the chronological position of the dated elements. The green and orange shading indicates an interpretation of the dating results.

Fig. 6. Kvæfjord 2 altarpiece. Mark on plank 14 (left wing, top plank of box).

				Z102003b	Z102001c	Z102002c	Z102018b	Z102004a	Z102006a	Z102005a	Z102007b	Z102015a	Z102016a	Z102014a	Z102012a	Z102010a
Same tree	Corpus back	plank 3	Z102003b	*	10,57	2,97	-	1,61	-	-	-	-	-	1,41	1,35	-
		plank 1	Z102001c	10,57	*	2,94	3,82	1,36	2,68	1,45	-	1,5	-	1,4	2,55	1,12
Z102M006 group 1	Tracery	plank 2	Z102002c	2,97	2,94	*	8,27	3,97	4,18	1,2	-	3,79	2,47	3	4,37	2,63
		tracery	Z102018b	-	3,82	8,27	*	3,9	3,09	2,17	-	3,25	2,68	2,77	3,74	2,82
	Corpus sides	plank 4	Z102004a	1,61	1,36	3,97	3,9	*	3,55	1,69	1,83	1,26	2,31	3,2	4,43	2,93
		plank 6	Z102006a	-	2,68	4,18	3,09	3,55	*	3,08	4,95	3,98	4,47	3,74	1,96	4,51
		plank 5	Z102005a	-	1,45	1,2	2,17	1,69	3,08	*	5,53	4,97	4,27	5,36	2,13	2,00
		plank 7	Z102007b	-	-	-	-	1,83	4,95	5,53	*	3,12	1,73	-	-	-
	Right wing	plank 11	Z102015a	-	1,5	3,79	3,25	1,26	3,98	4,97	3,12	*	5,48	4,27	3,54	2,65
		plank 8	Z102016a	-	-	2,47	2,68	2,31	4,47	4,27	1,73	5,48	*	6,49	3,1	4,02
		plank 10	Z102014a	1,41	1,4	3	2,77	3,2	3,74	5,36	-	4,27	6,49	*	3,37	2,21
	Left wing	plank 15	Z102012a	1,35	2,55	4,37	3,74	4,43	1,96	2,13	-	3,54	3,1	3,37	*	6,09
		plank 13	Z102010a	-	1,12	2,63	2,82	2,93	4,51	2,00	-	2,65	4,02	2,21	6,09	*

Table 1. Kvæfjord 2 altarpiece. Correlation between the tree-ring curves from each dated timber element with each other.

Oak provenance

Table 1 shows the correlation (t-value) between each of the dated tree-ring curves from the altarpiece with each other, at their cross-matched position. As mentioned above, the statistical agreement and the visual comparison of plots of the tree-ring curves from two of the backing planks is so similar, that they might come from a single tree, so these are averaged to form a single curve of 286 years in length, to represent that tree (Z102S001&3). The rest of the material is grouped to form an average (Z102M006) which is 229 years long. Correlation between the single tree and the rest of the material is not high, suggesting separate geographical sources for the two groups.

The correlation between these two averages and diverse oak chronologies and datasets from Northern Europe is shown in table 2. The large group is achieving highest correlation with a range of Southern Baltic tree-ring datasets including site chronologies from Northern Poland and the so-called “Baltic1” chronology, based on

artworks made from oak whose origin is somewhere in the Southern Baltic region but not yet precisely identified. The tree used for the two backing planks also matches best with Southern Baltic datasets, but with different ones to that of the main group. It seems to confirm that two sources for oak were utilised in the making of the Kvæfjord 2 altarpiece.

As the Kvæfjord 2 altarpiece is made from Southern Baltic oaks a sapwood estimate for the region around the mouth of the Vistula River is used (c. 15 sapwood years (-6 +9) (Wazny 1990)).

Filenames	-	-	Z102M006	Z102S001&3	
-	start	dates	AD1262	AD1199	
-	dates	end	AD1490	AD1484	
Z105M003	AD1266	AD1478	10,97	-	Tabernacle: Berg Norway (Daly 2014)
GAPCX7	AD1283	AD1450	10,49	-	Panels: Guthrie Aisle (Crone pers comm)
0EQKTVM001	AD1295	AD1549	8,67	-	Painted panel: Tallinn Christ Money-lenders (Daly & Läänelaid 2012)
P734001M	AD1246	AD1412	8,81	3,06	PL: Bransk (Wazny pers comm)
P815001M	AD1262	AD1503	8,23	-	PL: Bielsk Podl. (Wazny pers comm)
Z103M003	AD1234	AD1495	8,47	3,02	Altarpiece: Slagen altertavle Norge (Daly 2013b)
P835002m	AD1293	AD1477	8,07	-	PL: Tykocin (Wazny pers comm)
0075M0042012	AD1247	AD1455	7,81	-	Ship: Vejdyb group 4 (PL / Baltic 1) (Daly 1997)
stirlingdoorsM1	AD1270	AD1524	6,68	-	Furniture: Stirling doors (Crone pers comm)
0M040005	AD1257	AD1615	6,75	4,86	Baltic 2 (Hillam & Tyers 1995)
2129M001	AD1125	AD1399	6,68	-	Barrel: Niels Hemmingsensgade (Daly 2000)
0M040004	AD1156	AD1597	9,03	7,53	Baltic 1 (Hillam & Tyers 1995)
0075M0012012	AD1113	AD1463	7,06	8,02	Ship: Vejdyb group 1 (Baltic 1) (Daly 1997)
Z103M4&7&8	AD1351	AD1495	3,38	6,00	Altarpiece: Slagen altertavle Norge tracery (Daly 2013b)
0628002M	AD1225	AD1445	5,97	5,14	PL: Torun Joh Kir (Wazny pers comm)
P0011009	AD1103	AD1403	6,16	4,24	Timber cargo: Copper Ship Wainscot (Wazny pers comm)
0075M0032012	AD1221	AD1456	5,65	5,93	Ship: Vejdyb group 3 (Baltic 2) (Daly 1997)
HEADSx11	AD1304	AD1521	5,40	3,73	Sculpture: Stirling heads baltic (Crone pers comm)
HMC_T165	AD1078	AD1369	5,22	5,36	Coffin boards: Hull Baltic (Tyers pers comm)
Z084M002	AD1152	AD1438	4,64	5,31	Barrel: Skaftö wreck (Daly 2013a)
0670113M	AD1344	AD1613	4,13	5,88	Baltic 3 (Wazny pers comm)

Table 2. Kvæfjord 2 altarpiece, Oslo. Result of the correlation between the average of the tree-ring curves from the dated planks from the altarpiece (group 1 Z102M006 and same tree Z102S001&3) and diverse Northern European site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t-values.

Conclusion

Only timber elements that could be analysed non-invasively have been analysed in this investigation. A number of the elements analysed could not be dated, mostly from the wings. This might be due to the relatively fewer rings preserved on these pieces, but also might be due to difficulty in measuring the longitudinal sections of the oak anatomy. None of the sculptures (fig. 7) were analysed.

Several incised marks were observed on the structure and while the planks with one of these marks remains undated (fig. 6), it was found that two planks with marks might come from the same tree (fig. 3 and fig 9). One of these marks is only partially preserved due to the trimming of the plank during shaping (fig. 9), so it is unfortunately not quite possible to confirm that the marks are the same.

A different housemark is preserved on plank 7 on the corpus. The dendrochronological analysis indicates that the tree used for plank 7 grew in a different region to the tree for planks 1 and 3. It would be most useful if these housemarks could be identified, to enable insight into their geographical origin, and correlate this with the tree-ring evidence.

Fig. 7. Kvæfjord 2 altarpiece. Right wing.

Literature

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Fig. 8. Kvæfjord 2 altarpiece. Taking the macro photographs of the longitudinal section of the tree-rings on side plank 4. Traces of another house mark might be preserved on back plank 1.

Fig. 9. Kvæfjord 2 altarpiece. Partially preserved housemark on plank 1 (back plank of the corpus).

Filename	sample title and number	rings	start yr.	end yr.	conversion	pith	sapwood	bark?	extra start	extra end	interpretation / felling
Z102001c	Kvæfjord 2 altertavle Norge corpus back plank 1	286	AD1199	AD1484	?	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1494
Z102002c	Kvæfjord 2 altertavle Norge corpus back plank 2	142	AD1349	AD1490	?	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1500
Z102003b	Kvæfjord 2 altertavle Norge corpus back plank 3	273	AD1208	AD1480	?	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1494
Z102004a	Kvæfjord 2 altertavle Norge corpus side plank 4	165	AD1303	AD1467	?	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1477
Z102005a	Kvæfjord 2 altertavle Norge corpus side plank 5	219	AD1262	AD1480	?	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1490
Z102006a	Kvæfjord 2 altertavle Norge corpus side plank 6	178	AD1305	AD1482	?	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1492
Z102007b	Kvæfjord 2 altertavle Norge corpus side plank 7	207	AD1271	AD1477	?	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1487
Z1020089	Kvæfjord 2 altertavle Norge corpus stage	85			?	G	0	N	H1	H1	undated
Z102009b	Kvæfjord 2 altertavle Norge left wing side plank 12	80			?	G	0	N	H1	H1	undated
Z102010a	Kvæfjord 2 altertavle Norge left wing side plank 13	96	AD1387	AD1482	?	G	0	N	H5	H1	after AD1492
Z102011b	Kvæfjord 2 altertavle Norge left wing side plank 14	80			?	G	0	N	H1	H1	undated
Z102012a	Kvæfjord 2 altertavle Norge left wing side plank 15	97	AD1379	AD1475	?	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1485
Z102013a	Kvæfjord 2 altertavle Norge left wing stage	60			?	G	0	N	H1	H1	undated
Z102014a	Kvæfjord 2 altertavle Norge right wing side plank 10	99	AD1374	AD1472	?	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1482
Z102015a	Kvæfjord 2 altertavle Norge right wing side plank 11	57	AD1363	AD1419	?	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1429
Z102016a	Kvæfjord 2 altertavle Norge right wing side plank 8	101	AD1371	AD1471	?	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1481
Z102017a	Kvæfjord 2 altertavle Norge right wing side plank 9	76			?	G	0	N	H1	H1	undated
Z102018b	Kvæfjord 2 altertavle Norge corpus tracery	104	AD1348	AD1451	?	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1461
Z102M006 group 1	Z102M006 group 1 11 timber mean	229	AD1262	AD1490							
Z102S001 same tree 1&3	Kvæfjord 2 altertavle Norge corpus back planks 1&3 same tree	286	AD1199	AD1484	?	?	0	U	N	H1	after AD1494
Z102009b& 11b same tree	Kvæfjord 2 altertavle Norge left wing side planks 12&14 same tree	81			?	G	0	N	H1	H1	undated
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings.											
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Table 3. Kvæfjord 2 altarpiece, Oslo. List of objects analysed.